

Extraction and Photometric Method for the Simultaneous Determination of Palladium(II) and Platinum(IV) with Dibenzylidenethiocarbohydrazide

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Dibenzylidenethiocarbohydrazide (DBTCH) reacts with palladium(II) at room temperature in the pH range of 5.0-7.5 and with platinum(IV) under hot condition in the pH range of 5.8-6.8. The complexes are yellow in colour and are quantitatively extracted in ethyl acetate and chloroform respectively and exhibit maximum absorption at 370 nm. Both the metals form 1 : 2 complex (metal to ligand) with the ligand. The compositions of the complexes are established by mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods. The stepwise and overall formation constants of the complexes are determined by extended Yatsimirskii's, Leden's and Harvey-Manning's methods. It has been shown that DBTCH may be employed for simultaneous determination of palladium(II) and platinum(IV) by extractive spectrophotometric method. The effect of the other commonly associated ions in the determination of palladium and platinum have also been studied.

BEAMISH¹ reviewed the colorimetric methods for the determination of palladium(II) and platinum(IV) and only a few reagents had been recommended for the simultaneous determination of palladium and platinum. Recently α -benzoin oxime² was used as a chelating agent for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) and platinum(IV) in presence of each other. But the sensitivities of the reagent for the determination of palladium and platinum were low. Moreover, a number of commonly associated base metals and other platinum metals interfered with the determination. Mizuno and Miyatani³ recommended 4-(2-pyridylazo) resorcinol for successive spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) and platinum(IV). The sensitivity of the reagent was high for the determination of palladium but the presence of palladium gave a positive error in the determination of platinum and vice versa. 1,4-Diphenylthiosemicarbazide⁴ was also employed as a complexing agent for the simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) and platinum(IV).

Dibenzylidenethiocarbohydrazide (DBTCH), which was used as a sensitive and selective reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III)⁵, has been utilised as a very sensitive reagent for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) and platinum(IV). A method has been described for their simultaneous determination. The method is based on the fact that palladium(II) forms complex with DBTCH at room temperature and platinum(IV) forms complex with the reagent only on heating. The platinum content in the mixture should not exceed ten times by weight of palladium.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents : A Carl-Zeiss VSU spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm matched silica cells was used for absorbance measurements. The pH values of the solutions were measured with an expanded scale pH meter of Systronic.

The stock solutions of palladium(II) and platinum(IV) were prepared by dissolving 1.0 g each of palladium(II) chloride (J. M.) and chloroplatinic acid. The palladium(II) solution was standardised gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime⁶ and platinum(IV) solution by thiosalicylamide⁷ as chelating agents. Solutions for the spectrophotometric determinations were prepared by dilution of the stock solution with distilled water.

The reagent was insoluble in water and only moderately soluble in ethanol. A $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent solution was prepared in ethanol. All other chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade.

Buffer solution : 10% sodium acetate and 3 M hydrochloric acid solutions were used to adjust the solutions at different pH values.

Procedure :

Spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) : A known amount of palladium(II) solution (6.0-65 μg of metal) was taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel, diluted to 20 ml with distilled water and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.0-7.5. 2-3 ml ethanol and 2 ml reagent solution ($[R]/[M] \geq 5.0$) were added. The mixture was thoroughly mixed and allowed to stand for 2 hr, extracted thrice with 5 ml portions of ethylacetate

and washings collected in a 25 ml volumetric flask. It was made upto volume with ethylacetate, dried and absorbance was measured at 370 nm against the reagent blank.

Spectrophotometric determination of platinum(IV). An aliquot containing 10-175 μg of platinum(IV) was taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel, diluted to 20 ml with distilled water and pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.8-6.8. 2-3 ml ethanol and 2 ml reagent solution ($[\text{R}]/[\text{M}] \geq 5.0$) were added and heated over boiling water bath for 30 min. It was then cooled to room temperature and extracted thrice with 5 ml portions of chloroform and collected in a 25 ml volumetric flask. It was then diluted to the mark, dried and absorbance was measured at 370 nm against the reagent blank.

Simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) and platinum(IV) in a mixture. An aliquot containing known amount of palladium and platinum was taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel, diluted to 20 ml with distilled water and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.8-6.8. The palladium in the mixture was extracted and estimated according to the procedure described above. After the separation of palladium from the mixture, the platinum content in the residual aqueous phase was estimated according to the procedure described earlier.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves The absorbance curves of the extracts of palladium(II)-DBTCH complex in ethylacetate and platinum(IV)-DBTCH complex in chloroform and the absorbance curves of the reagent blanks are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively. Both the complexes showed maximum

Fig 1. Absorbance curves of Pd(II)-DBTCH complex and reagent blank in ethylacetate.

[Pd²⁺]: (I) $0.72 \times 10^{-5} M$, (II) $1.08 \times 10^{-5} M$,
(III) $1.44 \times 10^{-5} M$, (IV) $1.80 \times 10^{-5} M$,
(V) $2.16 \times 10^{-5} M$,
[DBTCH]: (VI) $1.08 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Fig 2. Absorbance curves of Pt(IV)-DBTCH complex and reagent blank in chloroform.

[Pt⁴⁺]: (I) $0.749 \times 10^{-5} M$, (II) $1.124 \times 10^{-5} M$,
(III) $1.498 \times 10^{-5} M$, (IV) $1.878 \times 10^{-5} M$,
(V) $2.248 \times 10^{-5} M$,
[DBTCH]: (VI) $1.124 \times 10^{-4} M$.

absorbance at 370 nm. The absorbance values of the reagent blanks were appreciably low in this region.

The effect of acidity, temperature, concentration of the reagent and the stability of the complexes: The study of the extraction behaviour of the complexes showed that quantitative extraction of palladium(II)-DBTCH complex occurred at pH 5.0-7.5 and platinum complex at pH 5.8-6.8.

Palladium formed a yellow coloured complex with DBTCH instantaneously at room temperature. The reaction was slow. The reaction mixture should be allowed to stand for at least 1.5 hr to attain maximum complex formation. The complex decomposed at higher temperature. Platinum did not form any complex with DBTCH at room temperature even on prolonged standing and at least 30 min of heating over boiling water bath was necessary for complete formation of the complex.

For maximal development of colour and for complete extraction of both the complexes the molar ratio of reagent to metal should exceed 5 : 1. Both the complexes were stable and the colour intensities of the complexes were constant over the studied 24 hr period.

Effect of solvents: Ethylacetate and chloroform were taken as working solvents for the extraction of palladium and platinum complexes respectively. Behaviour of a few other solvents along with ethylacetate and chloroform towards extraction of the complexes are shown in Table 1.

Calibration curve, optimum range and photometric error: Both palladium(II)- and platinum(IV)-DBTCH complexes obeyed the Beer's law at 370 nm over the concentration ranges of 0.2-3.0 ppm of palladium(II) and 0.5-7.0 ppm of platinum(IV) respectively.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTIONS OF THE PALLADIUM(II)- AND PLATINUM(IV)-DBTCH COMPLEXES IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	Pd(II)DBTCH complex		Pt(IV)-DBTCH complex	
	Distribution ratio	% Extracted	Distribution ratio	% Extracted
Benzene	2.578	72.04	4.58	81.98
Chloroform	21.01	96.01	181.7	99.5
1,2-Dichloroethane	7.5	88.2	35.52	97.25
Ethylacetate	71.0	93.6	548	99.8
Isobutyl methyl ketone	6.075	85.9	2.45	71.0

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ANALYTICAL METHODS FOR THE DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM AND PLATINUM WITH DBTCH

Type of the complex	Molar absorptivity 1 mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Sandell's sensitivity μg cm ⁻²	Relative mean error %	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation %
Pd(II)-DBTCH	4.268 × 10 ⁴	0.0025	1.04	0.32	1.12
Pt(IV)-DBTCH	3.9768 × 10 ⁴	0.0065	0.55	0.28	0.51

TABLE 3—STEPWISE AND OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR PALLADIUM(II) AND PLATINUM(IV) COMPLEXES AT 27 ± 2°

Method	Palladium(II)-DBTCH			Platinum(IV)-DBTCH		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
Yatsimirskii's	5.6108	5.3280	10.9288	5.8771	5.4860	11.8631
Leden's	5.6282	5.3810	10.9542	5.8062	5.8177	11.1239
Harvey-Manning's	5.7057	5.7057	11.4115	5.7759	5.7759	11.5518

The optimum concentration ranges with the highest accuracy as evaluated from Ringbom's curve were 0.6-2.0 ppm for palladium(II) complex and 1.6-5.0 ppm for platinum(IV) complex. The corresponding values of relative analysis error per one percent photometric error according to Ayre's equation were 2.73% for the determination of 1.0 ppm palladium and 2.72% for the determination of 3.0 ppm platinum.

Characteristics of the analytical methods: Molar absorptivity of the complex and the sensitivity¹⁰ of the colour reaction are shown in Table 2. The relative mean errors and the relative standard deviations obtained from five identical sets of experiments are also given.

Five determinations with 28.8 μg of palladium gave an average of 28.53 μg which varied between 28.53 ± 0.30 μg at 90% confidence limit.

With 54.8 μg platinum the average values was 54.5 μg which varied between 54.5 ± 0.27 μg at 90% confidence limit.

Nature and composition of the complexes and their successive formation constants: The composition of the palladium(II)- and platinum(IV)-DBTCH complexes were studied by mole-ratio¹¹ method and verified by slope-ratio¹² method. It was found that in both cases a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex was formed.

The conditional stepwise stability constants of the complexes were computed from spectrophotometric data of Yatsimirskii's^{13,14} and Ledem's¹⁵ method. The results of all the systems along with

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM(II) AND PLATINUM(IV)

Foreign ion added	Amount (in mg) tolerated in the determination of	
	Palladium(II) [Pd = 28.8 μg]	Platinum(IV) [Pt = 54.8 μg]
Tl(IV)	1.0 ^b	1.0 ^b
V(V)	2.5	1.0
Cr(III)	1.0 ^b	1.0 ^b
Mn(II)	1.0 ^b	1.0 ^b
Fe(III)	1.0 ^b	1.0 ^b
Co(II)	1.0 ^a	1.0 ^a
Ni(II)	1.0 ^a	1.0 ^a
Cu(II)	0.15 ^d	0.10 ^d
Zn(II)	2.5 ^a	1.0 ^a
Cd(II)	2.5 ^a	1.0 ^a
Hg(II)	0.5 ^a	0.5 ^a
Pb(II)	1.0 ^{a,b}	1.0 ^{a,b}
Mo(VI)	1.5	1.0
W(VI)	1.5	1.0
U(VI)	1.5	1.0
Os(VI)	1.0 ^a	nil
Pd(II)	—	nil
Pt(IV)	0.80	—
Ru(III)	0.20 ^f	0.05 ^f
Rh(III)	nil	nil
Ir(III)	0.50	nil
Citrate	200	100
Oxalate	200	100
Tartrate	1000	500
Phosphate	200	200
EDTA	50	50
Fluoride	500	500
Iodide	2000	2000

a = in presence of Ca-EDTA ; b = in presence of tartarate ;
c = in presence of iodide ; d = in presence of Na₂-EDTA ;
e = prior reduction with SO₂ ; f = in presence of citrate.

the values of overall stability constants by Harvey-Manning's method are compiled in Table 3.

Effect of diverse ions : In the study of the effect of diverse ions, the standard palladium(II) and platinum(IV) solutions containing known amounts of metals were mixed with varying amounts of diverse ions and the recommended procedures were followed. The tolerance limits (i.e. concentrations of the diverse ions causing an error of less than $\pm 2\%$ in the transmittance value) are recorded in Table 4.

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